

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

Transcriptome analysis of diabetes type 1 patients and mouse models

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

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Based on

Based on Standard DMP template for Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BB-SRC) 2024

UK Research
and Innovation

Funded by the [ELIXIR-UK: FAIR Data Stewardship training UKRI award](#) (MR/V038966/1) and BioFAIR

(Q1) Proposal name

Transcriptomics of diabetes type 1 patients and mouse models.

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

This is a transcriptomic study of diabetes type I in humans and mouse models using bulk RNAseq and expression microarrays.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

This study will generate quantitative measurements of gene/transcript expression from human blood using bulk RNAseq. This study will also use mouse gene/transcript expression data from publicly available microarray and bulk RNAseq studies.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

New primary data (FASTQ) will be generated for human blood. This study will also use mouse gene/transcript expression data from publicly available microarray and bulk RNAseq studies.

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

- **Human bulk RNAseq:**
 - **Platform:** Illumina HiSeq 2500 (100bp paired-end, sequencing depth of ~45M read pairs).
 - **Data format:** compressed FASTQ.
 - **Scale:** 12 control samples (patients) and 12 disease samples (diabetes type 1 patients).
 - **TOTAL file size:** estimated 150GB.
- **Mouse transcriptomics:** (these are public datasets from ArrayExpress and GEO, and will not be archived by this study):
 - **Platforms:** mixed (both expression microarray and RNAseq).
 - **Data formats:** compressed FASTQ, CEL, text.
 - **Scale:** estimated 50 samples.
 - **TOTAL file size:** estimated 100-400GB.

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

Compressed FASTQ files (format definition: doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkp1137) from human bulk RNAseq will be treated as sensitive genetic data. All data will be stored and managed (replicated) over 2 remote sites using the University Research Data Store (RDS) where “snapshot” copies are taken on a daily basis to mitigate the

risk of data loss or corruption. Access is authenticated through the University username and password processes, which has been assessed as suitable for the storage of highly sensitive data.

Each dataset generated will receive a globally unique identifier and be catalogued in a spreadsheet with provenance and detailed metadata.

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

RNAseq data and associated metadata will be annotated to the level required by the public repository, ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress) employing the community metadata standard: MINSEQE (doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5706412).

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

All data generated will be bulk RNAseq. All raw data (FASTQ) and processed data (gene/transcript unnormalised counts) will be stored long-term in the public repository, ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress). Local copies of this data and metadata will be archived in the University data store for 10 years from the last point of access.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

All data generated will be bulk RNAseq. All raw data (FASTQ) and processed data (gene/transcript unnormalised counts) will be available to all via the public repository, ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress).

(Q10) When will data be available?

Data will be shared publicly via ArrayExpress at the time of publication or within 3 years of its generation. No identifiable data will be made available.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

All raw data (FASTQ) and processed data (gene/transcript unnormalised counts) will be discoverable and accessible in the indexed public repository, ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress).

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

Metadata required for appropriate reuse and the use of interoperable data formats (MINSEQE) will

accompany all data submitted to the public repository, ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress).

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

We envisage no restrictions or delays to data sharing.

(Q14) Secondary use

New data generated in this study does not currently exist in the public domain for secondary use by other researchers. This data will be of benefit for the diabetes type 1 research community.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

None identified.

(Q16) Main risks to data security

The University research data store described enables secure, replicated storage of sensitive data. Raw genetic data (FASTQ) generated by this study will not be stored on personal computers or external hard drives. All human participants will be given a unique pseudonymised ID. The mapping between this ID and identifiable participant information (including name and address) will be managed by the study clinician and no other researcher will have access to these records.

We note that DOB will be translated to “age in years” by the clinician and shared for the purpose of the study. RNAseq data for patients will be categorised as genetic information and consent will be requested for use. Ethical approval will be obtained before data collection commences. Consent forms and Patient Information Sheets (PIS) will state that pseudonymised data will be shared with others through publication in data repositories.

(Q17) Capabilities

The University provides a secure, replicated data store supported by University staff. The institution also provides a research data repository service which is available to all researchers for the publishing of datasets. The University’s Open Data team offer centralised support and advice around research data management at all stages of the research lifecycle.

An Information Security Policy and Framework is in place, including mandatory annual training for all staff, with the aim of ensuring the protection of the University’s members, data and devices.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

Weekly project meetings will include a data management agenda item enabling revision and review of data management as and when. Data Stewardship Wizard will be used to enable and track changes and FAIRification of data and metadata.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

The university holds an up-to-date, externally-audited ISO 14001 certified environmental management system, which has been held continuously since 2013. This covers good practice and continual improvement on all of the University's environmental aspects including energy, procurement, pollution, travel, waste, water and biodiversity.